

CRYSTALLISATION OF TiO₂ XEROGEL

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ABSTRACT

Nanomaterials based on titanium dioxide has a wide usage, mainly in the form of films in the solar systems and environmental applications. In these films, TiO₂ is required to be in the form of anatase. This crystalline form is formed in the films during their thermal treatment. Sol-gel method represents advantageous method for preparation of TiO₂ films. In this method, the controlled reactions of hydrolysis and condensation of titanium isopropoxide lead to preparation of TiO₂ sol which is transformed to gel and subsequently to xerogel after the sol is deposited on the substrate. Mentioned transformation is carried out by drying up to the temperatures of 100 °C. The subsequent thermal treatment at temperatures around the 400 °C causes the transformation of xerogel to anatase. For achievement of the best properties of prepared films, the process of thermal treatment has to be controlled. For optimizing of thermal treatment process, it is needed to understand and observe which processes take place during the transformation from xerogel to crystalline form – anatase.

Processes which take place during the thermal treatment of xerogel were observed using DTA/TG analysis at heating rates of 10 and 2 °C/min. On the basis of analysis of DTA/TG curves, the individual processes during the thermal treatment have been identified. It was found, that in the range of temperatures, where the crystallization of anatase is assumed, there are also the processes which are connected with weight loss. Based on the mentioned fact, the process of thermal treatment of TiO₂ xerogel was observed using high-temperature Raman spectroscopy and high-temperature X-ray diffraction. In relation to the formation of anatase, the intervals of temperatures were identified. Based on the comparison of results of all analyses, it can be concluded that the anatase is formed from xerogel by the given reactions – the first reaction represents the decomposition of xerogel leading to the formation of amorphous TiO₂ and the second reaction represents the formation of anatase, respectively.

Keywords: Titania xerogel, Crystalization, Sol-gel, DTA/TG, Raman spectroscopy, HTXRD

Acknowledgment: The research was supported by the projects VEGA 1/0589/17 and VEGA 1/0431/18.

This paper is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#).
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566.